

Utilization of wood ash as soil amendment and fertilizer on some growth and physiological indices of *Capsicum annum* (pepper)

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Abstract

Sustainable utilization of wastes such as wood ash generated by small scale industries is an innovative method of waste management. This study elucidated effects of varying levels (250 mL WALF + 750 Water, 500 mL WALF + 500 mL Water, 750 mL WALF+ 250 mL Water, 1000mL WALF) of inclusion of wood ash liquid fertilizer (WALF) on cultivation of *C. annum* (pepper). Distilled water served as control. Agronomical and physiological parameters of the pepper were determined. Height (18.82 cm), number of leaf (16.60), leaf breadth (3.58 cm), and stem girth (0.90 cm) of the pepper treated with combination 500 mL WALF + 500 mL Water were significantly higher compared with other combinations of the WALF. Similar observation was noticed in chlorophyll ($13.6 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2}$) contents determined in the leaves of the pepper treated with the same combination. Higher net assimilation rate ($0.80 \text{ gm}^{-2}\text{day}^{-1}$), relative growth rate ($0.78 \text{ mgg}^{-1}\text{day}^{-1}$), leaf area ratio ($0.08 \text{ m}^2\text{kg}^{-1}$), leaf area (83.56 cm^2) and specific leaf area ($142.56\text{m}^2.\text{kg}^{-1}$) were observed in the leaves of the pepper treated with 500 mL WALF + 500 mL Water. In conclusion the 500 mL WALF + 500 mL Water enhanced better the agronomic and physiological parameters of the vegetable, therefore, the combination is recommended for sustainable cultivation of pepper.

Keywords: growth component, wood ash, liquid fertilizer, waste management, morphological character, vegetables, innovation

Introduction

Management of industrial wastes has significant effects on survival of flora and fauna found in our environment. The effects therefore motivate the sustainable usage of plant-based wastes to enhance production of vegetables such as *Capsicum annum* as one the commonly cultivated peppers. *C. annum* is an annual tropical vegetable grown for its sensory attributes and for preservation of agricultural products in organic farming systems (Ademoyegu et al., 2011; Idowu-Agida et al., 2012, Sanusi and Ayinde, 2013). Despite the economic importance of the vegetable, there is low production of the crop due to poor land practice, insufficient fertilizers or high cost of inorganic fertilizers, inappropriate quantity of the fertilizers and their possible deleterious effects on soil microorganism if applied inappropriately.

Over the years, over cropping or intensive cultivation of vegetables including *C. annuum* on certain areas of land most especially in urban areas has resulted into depletion of soil nutrients and increase in soil acidity. Incidentally, the supply of organic manure is not enough, especially in urban areas where agricultural land is limited in nutritional contents to substitute the use of chemical fertilizer and as a quick means of nutrient replenishment. Therefore, application of organic fertilizer such as wood ash may help in coping with the low level of nutrients in the soil (Witt et al., 2005). According to Okore et al. (2012), vegetables and spices such as pepper take up large amount of nutrients from the soil hence the need for replacement of such soil with organic substances through introduction of plant-based wastes such as wood ash (Ademoyegun et al., 2011) to augment mineral elements depleted in the soil (Jacobson, 2001, Adekayode and Olojugba, 2010).

In the recent times, there has been a clarion call for sustainable utilization of natural resources in farming as biotechnological approach towards recycling to meet up with food demands of geometric increase in population, gradual reduction or extinction of natural resources. Lack of agricultural inputs such as fertilizers contributed largely to low farm produce, less quality of produce and increase in food insecurity in Nigeria.

In addition, many local farmers cannot afford the exorbitant prices of synthetic fertilizers talk less of preventing their adverse effects on the produce. Therefore, there is urgent need to adopt the usage of organic fertilizer of plant origin such as wood ash as source of soil amendment. Disposal of wood ash as a product of complete combustion of timber is an environmental threat especially in an area where small scale industries such as bakeries, charcoal production companies and food canteens which cannot afford increasing price of gas and other technology driven sources of fuel are very common. On the basis of these, there is need to assess sustainable usage of wood ash as soil amendments in other to increase crop production among local farmers. Hence, this study evaluated effects of wood ash liquid fertilizer as soil amendment on agronomic and physiological parameters of *C. annuum*.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

The study was conducted in the green house of Department of Botany, Lagos State University, Ojo campus. The geographical references of latitude and longitude of the study area are 6.4668. N6⁰ 28'0.760" and 3.19917 E3⁰ 11'57.006" respectively.

Sources of Seeds

Seeds of *C. annuum* were collected from Abule, Ojoo, along Federal University of Agriculture Alabata, Abeokuta, Ogun State, Nigeria. The seeds were identified at Forestry Research Institute of Nigeria (FRIN), Ibadan, Nigeria. The voucher number of the seed is FHI-51380.

Soil collection

Top soil was collected from areas of the botanical garden of Department of Botany, Lagos State University, Ojo campus. From 500 m apart, top soil was collected at the botanical garden using soil probe as described by Ojewumi et al., (2022). The soil samples were sterilized using the autoclave at 132 °C for 30 minutes.

Preparation for Planting

The soil was poured into twenty five perforated planting buckets. Both the planting buckets and soil weighed 10kg. The perforation allowed drainage and soil aeration without reducing the soil quantity and quality.

Nursery preparation

Seedlings of *C. annum* were raised in the green house of Department of Botany, Lagos State University, Ojo, Lagos for three weeks. The seedlings were randomly transplanted into the planting buckets when they were 14.5 cm high. The seedlings were thereafter watered for one week to ensure acclimatization of the seedling to the planting buckets.

Experimental design

The planting buckets with one seedling each were arranged in a completely randomized design with five replicates. Also, temperature of the green house was 28 °C in the day and 21 °C in the night while relative humidity ranged from of 65–75%.

Preparation and application of wood ash liquid fertilizer.

Procedure of Ojewumi and Oyetunji,(2022) was modified and used to determine wood ash liquid fertilizer used for this study. Wood ash was obtained from small scale industries in Ojo, Lagos and thoroughly sieved to remove pebbles, then 1000 g of the sieved wood ash was weighed, diluted with 2L of water, mixed thoroughly and filtered. The residue was discarded while the filtrate(wood ash liquid) was used to constitute different level (250 mL liquid wood ash+750 mL water, 500 mL liquid wood ash +500 mL water, 750 mL liquid wood ash +250 mL water, and 1000 mL liquid wood ash) of wood ash liquid fertilizer (filtrates).. Distilled water served as control.

The planting buckets containing one seedling each were divided into five (5) groups and each experimental unit was exogenously applied with one combination of the wood ash liquid fertilizer produced. Seedlings in each group were applied with 50 mL of wood ash liquid fertilizer of each of the combinations prepared above.

Data collection

Parameters such as plant height, number of leaf, leaf breadth and leaf area were measured. Also, Stem girth was measured using a venire caliper according to the methods of Kadiri (2014). Fresh weight of root and shoot were recorded using sensitive weighing scale. Leaf breadth of controlled and treated plants were measured according to methods of Kadiri (1999) using a thread and a meter rule calibrated in centimeter.

Determination of total leaf area, specific leaf area and leaf area index of pepper leaves.

A portable Leaf Area Meter (LI-3000 C) manufactured by DMP Ltd was used to determine the leaf area of the seedlings (Ojewumi et al., 2022). Using the leaf area values and weight of leaves, physiological parameters such as specific leaf area (SLA) and leaf area index (LAI) were computed according to methods described by Alireza et al., (2012) as shown below

$$\text{Specific leaf area (SLA)} = \frac{\text{Leaf area(LA)}}{\text{Corresponding weight of leaf(WL)}} \dots\dots\dots (1),$$

where LA = Leaf Area; W_L = Corresponding weight of leaf

$$\text{Leaf Area Index (LAI)} = \frac{\text{Leaf area(LA)}}{\text{Area of litter fall}} \dots\dots\dots (2).$$

Determination of net assimilation rate and relative growth rate

The mean values of fresh weights, leaf areas and times of harvest parameters from 5 replicates were used to calculate the following components of growth analysis as described by Badr et al.(1998).

Relative Growth Rate (RGR), Assimilation Rate (NGR) and Leaf Area Ratio (LAR).

Relative Growth Rate (RGR)

Relative growth rate (RGR) was calculated from the measured values of fresh weight of plants (W₁ and W₂) at time t₁ and t₂ using the mathematical relationship below.

$$\text{RGR} = \frac{\text{Loge}W_2 - \text{Loge}W_1}{t_2 - t_1} \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

Net Assimilation Rate

The Net Assimilation Rate (NAR) was calculated from the measured values of leaf area (A_1 and A_2), fresh weight of plants (W_1 and W_2) and time (t_1 and t_2).using the relationship below.

$$\text{NAR} = \frac{W_2 - W_1}{A_2 - A_1} \cdot \frac{\text{Loge}A_2 - \text{Loge}A_1}{t_2 - t_1} \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

The Leaf Area Ratio (LAR) was also calculated from the measured values of leaf area (A_1 and A_2), fresh weight of plants (W_1 and W_2) and time (t_1 and t_2) using the relationship below.

$$\text{LAR} = \frac{W_2 - W_1}{t_2 - t_1} \cdot \frac{\text{Loge}A_2 - \text{Loge}A_1}{W_2 - W_1} \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

Determination of chlorophyll contents in *Capsicum annum*

One gram each of fresh leaf of treated and control plants were obtained from the harvested *C. annum*. The leaves were crushed separately in a clean mortar with 40 mL of 80% (v/v) acetone. The resulting green liquid was transferred into a Buchner Funnel containing a pad of whatman No. 1 filter paper and filtered. The residual pulp was re-extracted with 20 mL aliquot of 80 % acetone and filtered into the previous filtrate. The optical density of the chlorophyll extract in a 10 mm cell was determined with a spectrophotometer set at 652 nm and the amount of chlorophyll present in the leaf was calculated according to Yang *et al.* (2009) using the formula below:

$$\text{Mg total chlorophyll/g tissue} = \frac{0.D.652 \times 1000 \times V}{34.5 \times 1000 \times W} \dots\dots\dots (6)$$

Where:

O.D = Optical density reading of chlorophyll extract at 652nm

V = the final volume of the chlorophyll extract

W = the fresh weight (in grams) of the leaf tissue extracted.

Statistical analysis

Data obtained we reanalyzed using statistical analysis system (SAS, 2013). Means were calculated using one way analysis of variance and separated using Duncan's Multiple Range Test(DMRT) at $P < 0.05$.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 showed that the soil used was acidic (pH; 4.3), organic carbon content was 15.4g kg with total nitrogen (1.3g kg⁻¹) and available phosphorus of 19.7g kg⁻¹. The textural properties of the soil showed that the soil is sandy loam constituting 830g kg⁻¹ sandy, 39 g kg⁻¹,clay and 131g kg⁻¹silt.

The nutritional elements compositions of the soil in terms of potassium, calcium, sodium and magnesium were relatively low. Figure 1 showed that the nutrients and physicochemical contents of wood ash liquid fertilizer were relatively higher than that reported in the soil.

The morphological parameters such as plant height of pepper as influenced by wood ash liquid fertilizer (WALF) application is represented in table 2. It was observed that there was no significant

variation ($p>0.5$) in the height of the pepper treated with different combinations of the WALF at 2 weeks after treatment (WAT). The treatments had significant increase on the parameter treated with combination 500 mL WALF + 500 mL Water) at 4WAT (17.80 cm) and 6 WAT (19.62 cm) compared with other treatments. Similar observation was noticed on number of leaf, leaf length, stem girth and petiole length of pepper treated using WALF at 2 and 4 WAT. Higher number of leaf (16.60), leaf length (3.58 cm), stem girth (1.12 cm) and petiole length (5.62 cm) were recorded in pepper treated with 500 mL WALF+500 mL Water (Table 3). Similar trend was noticed on the effect of the treatment on the leaf breadth (3.58 cm) of the plant (Tables 4).

Effects of different concentrations of wood ash liquid fertilizer on physiological parameters of pepper

Chlorophyll ($13.6 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2}$) was significantly higher in the leaves of the pepper treated with 500 mL WALF+ 500 mL Water followed by control ($10.90 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2}$) (Figure 2). Higher net assimilation rate ($0.80 \text{ gm}^{-2}\text{day}^{-1}$), relative growth rate ($0.78\text{mgg}^{-1}\text{day}^{-1}$) and leaf area ratio ($0.08 \text{ m}^2\text{kg}^{-1}$) were recorded in the leaves of pepper treated with 500 mL WALF+500 mL Water compared with lower or higher concentration of the WALF (Table 8). Also, the treatments had significant increase on Leaf area (78.08 cm^2) and Specific leaf area ($160.56 \text{ m}^2.\text{kg}^{-1}$) of the pepper treated with 500 mL WALF+ 500 mL Water at 8WAT. Similar observation was noticed on the effects of the treatments on Leaf area (83.56 cm^2) and Specific leaf area ($142.56 \text{ m}^2.\text{kg}^{-1}$) of the pepper at 10 WAT (Table 9).

Table 1. The physical and chemical properties of the soil used for the experiment

Parameters	Quantities
pH (H ₂ O) (1.1)	4.3±1.23
Organic Carbon (g kg ⁻¹)	15.4±1.74
Total N (g kg ⁻¹)	1.3±0.96
Available P (mg kg ⁻¹)	19.7±1.56
Particle size distribution (g kg ⁻¹)	
Sand	830±2.85
Clay	39±1.45
Silt	131±2.95
Textural class	Sandy Loam
Exchangeable Bases (cmol kg ⁻¹)	
Potassium	0.33±0.02
Calcium	6.34±1.45
Sodium	0.50±0.04
Magnesium	0.61±0.03

Table 2. Effects of varying concentrations of wood ash liquid fertilizer on height of pepper

Treatments (mL)	Weeks after treatment		
	2	4	6
250 WALF +750 Water	13.76±0.66 ^a	14.92±0.66 ^a	14.96±0.72 ^{ab}
500 WALF +500 Water	13.52±1.25 ^a	17.80±1.86 ^a	19.62±0.56 ^a
750 WALF +250	13.08±0.25 ^a	6.04±1.00 ^b	15.88±1.23 ^b
1000 WALF	13.64±0.67 ^a	14.52±1.00 ^{ab}	12.04±0.73 ^c
Control (Ordinary water)	15.64±1.40 ^a	16.68±1.63 ^a	18.82±0.64 ^a

Means \pm standard error followed by different superscripts in the same columns are significantly different at $p < 0.05$ according to Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT) WALF=Wood ash liquid fertilizer

Figure 1. Exchangeable nutrients and physicochemical contents of wood ash liquid fertilizer

Table 3. Effects of varying concentrations of wood ash liquid fertilizer on number of leaf of pepper

Treatments (mL)	Weeks after treatment		
	2	4	6
250 WALF +750 Water	7.60 \pm 1.02 ^a	11.00 \pm 0.70 ^a	11.20 \pm 0.86 ^b
500 WALF +500 Water	9.00 \pm 1.26 ^a	12.00 \pm 3.42 ^a	16.60 \pm 0.50 ^a
750 WALF +250	10.00 \pm 0.83 ^a	13.80 \pm 1.15 ^a	12.20 \pm 0.58 ^b
1000 WALF	7.60 \pm 1.16 ^a	10.20 \pm 1.59 ^a	10.60 \pm 1.60 ^b
Control (Ordinary water)	7.60 \pm 1.53 ^a	12.80 \pm 1.2 ^a	12.40 \pm 1.36 ^b

Means \pm standard error followed by different superscripts in the same columns are significantly different at $p < 0.05$ according to Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT) WALF=Wood ash liquid fertilizer.

Table 4. Effects of varying concentrations of wood ash fertilizer on leaf length of pepper

Treatments (mL)	Weeks after treatment		
	2	4	6
250 WALF +750 Water	4.16 \pm 0.70 ^a	2.74 \pm 0.16 ^a	2.00 \pm 0.16 ^b
500 WALF +500 Water	4.10 \pm 1.07 ^a	2.86 \pm 0.42 ^a	3.58 \pm 0.32 ^a
750 WALF +250 Water	3.66 \pm 0.50 ^a	2.96 \pm 0.32 ^a	2.20 \pm 1.20 ^{ab}
1000 WALF	3.46 \pm 0.50 ^a	2.46 \pm 0.38 ^a	2.32 \pm 0.40 ^{ab}
Control (Ordinary water)	2.96 \pm 0.31 ^a	2.88 \pm 0.26 ^a	2.50 \pm 0.40 ^{ab}

Means \pm standard error followed by different superscripts in the same columns are significantly different at $p < 0.05$ according to Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT) WALF=Wood ash liquid fertilizer.

Table 5. Effects of varying concentrations of wood ash liquid fertilizer on leaf breadth of pepper

Treatments (mL)	Weeks after treatment		
	2	4	6
250 WALF +750 Water	1.62±0.20 ^a	2.00±0.20 ^a	2.00±0.20 ^{ab}
500 WALF +500 Water	2.02±0.50 ^a	2.60±0.33 ^a	3.58±0.32 ^a
750 WALF +250 Water	1.66±0.30 ^a	2.16±0.40 ^a	2.50±0.40 ^{ab}
1000 WALF	1.46±0.23 ^a	2.38±0.40 ^a	2.32±0.40 ^{ab}
Control (Ordinary water)	1.36±0.30 ^a	1.80±0.70 ^a	2.20±1.22 ^{ab}

Means ± standard error followed by different superscripts in the same columns are significantly deferent at $p < 0.05$ according to Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT) WALF=Wood ash liquid fertilizer.

Table 6. Effects of varying concentrations of wood ash liquid fertilizer on stem girth of pepper

Treatments (mL)	Weeks after treatment		
	2 WAT	4WAT	6WAT
250 WALF +750 Water	0.62±0.10 ^a	0.80±0.70 ^{ab}	0.80±0.10 ^b
500 WALF +500 Water	0.78±0.40 ^b	0.90±0.13 ^a	1.12±0.10 ^a
750 WALF +250 Water	0.64±0.1 ^{ab}	0.78±0.73 ^{ab}	0.68±0.11 ^b
1000 WALF	0.58±0.03 ^a	0.68±0.10 ^c	0.72±0.04 ^b
Control (Ordinary water)	0.72±0.05 ^{ab}	0.78±0.80 ^{ab}	0.96±0.14 ^{ab}

Means ± standard error followed by different superscripts in the same columns are significantly deferent at $p < 0.05$ according to Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT) WALF=Wood ash liquid fertilizer,

Table 7. Effect of different concentrations of wood ash liquid fertilizer on petiole length of pepper

Treatments (mL)	Weeks after treatment		
	2	4	6
250 WALF +750 Water	2.36±0.40 ^a	3.48±0.8 ^a	4.54±0.81 ^b
500 WALF +500 Water	1.48±0.33 ^{ab}	4.96±1.22 ^a	5.62±1.34 ^a
750 WALF +250 Water	1.24±0.20 ^b	4.00±1.10 ^a	4.70±0.98 ^b
1000 WALF	1.60±0.31 ^{ab}	3.28±0.80 ^a	3.30±0.80 ^a
Control (Ordinary water)	0.88±0.20 ^b	3.62±0.93 ^a	5.00±0.42 ^{ab}

Means ± standard error followed by different superscripts in the same columns are significantly deferent at $p < 0.05$ according to Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT)WALF=Wood ash liquid fertilizer,

Figure 2. Effects of different concentrations of wood ash liquid fertilizer on chlorophyll contents of pepper. WALF=Wood ash liquid fertilizer.

Table 8. Effect of different concentrations of wood ash liquid fertilizer on Growth parameters and some Physiological Parameters of Pepper leaves

Treatments (mL)	8WAT		10WAT		NAR(gm ² day ⁻¹)	RGR(Mgg ⁻¹ day ⁻¹)	LAR(m ² kg ⁻¹)
	Leaf area(cm)	Specific leaf	Leaf area(cm)	Specific leaf			
250 WALF + 750 Water	60.12±5.39 ^b	116.70±2.79 ^b	63.48±1.48 ^b	73.12±1.47 ^d	0.58±0.31 ^{ab}	0.20±0.10 ^b	0.02±0.01 ^b
500 WALF + 500 Water	78.08±4.46 ^a	160.56±3.40 ^a	83.56±1.93 ^a	142.56±2.59 ^a	0.80±0.37 ^a	0.78±0.49 ^b	0.08±0.02 ^a
750 WALF + 250 Water	54.76±0.97 ^c	120.86±4.36 ^a	56.24±2.64 ^c	103.60±1.15 ^c	0.66±0.54 ^{ab}	0.19±0.10 ^b	0.02±0.01 ^b
1000 WALF	51.34±1.44 ^c	84.45±1.27 ^a	36.56±7.23 ^d	70.96±2.08 ^d	0.44±0.30 ^b	0.21±0.05 ^b	0.02±0.01 ^b
Control (Ordinary water)	54.84±4.73 ^c	100.08±2.23 ^{ac}	54.86±6.45 ^c	112.48±5.29 ^b	0.20±0.00 ^a	0.78±0.04 ^a	0.04±0.01 ^{ab}

Means ± standard error followed by different superscripts in the same columns are significantly deferent at $p < 0.05$ according to Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT) WALF=Wood ash liquid fertilizer, WAT= Weeks after treatment

Discussion

Sustainable usage of waste products such as wood ash generated by small scale industries is an innovative approach towards improvement of crop production and reduction of food insecurity most especially in developing countries such as Nigeria. Analysis of soil where this study was carried out indicates that textural properties of the soil can hold moisture or water needed for cultivation of crops such as pepper yet the mineral composition may not be adequate to meet nutritional requirement for cultivation of most vegetables (Olugbemi, 2019). This observation therefore could be regarded as reasonable justification for enhancement of the soil using plant based organic material such as wood ash (Olugbemi, 2019).

These findings also showed influence of wood ash on soil enrichment for proper growth, development of physiological parameters and yield of the pepper. Better performance of agronomic characters such as height, number of leaf and leaf area recorded in pepper treated with combination 500 mL WALF + 500 mL Water may indicate that the combination contained higher nutritional contents required for growth and development of pepper. This is in agreement with submission of Moure et al.(2020) who opined that two different blending combinations of food waste and agro-industrial waste digestates, and wood ashes released nutrients to plants than when each of them was used singly. Mbah et al. (2009) and Nweke et al. (2017) also reported that application of combinations of poultry manure improved better maize growth and yield.

In a similar order, higher leaf length, leaf breadth, stem girth and petiole length recorded in the pepper treated with 500 mL WALF + 500 mL Water at 6 WAT compared with other treatments may be due to the presence of appreciable amount of exchangeable minerals recorded in the filtrates of the ash as a required factor for tissue development of the vegetable. Also, an increase in number of leaf per plant observed in the pepper as affected by application of WALF is in agreement with submissions of Makinde (2007) and Jenni et al. (2008) who posited that synergy of combination of poultry manure and cow dung improved vegetative growth of crops. This observation infers that nutrient depleted soil could be enriched using ash to introduce nutrients to the soil thereby influencing the morphological characters and other functional units of plants (Saarsalmi et al., 2001).

Furthermore, 1000 mL WALF reduced morphological and physiological characters of the pepper. The reduction may indicate that the concentration of the treatment was higher than maximum requirement of the vegetable which eventually retarded or inhibited general development of the vegetables. Also, application of 50 mL of 1000 mL WALF might have interacted negatively with tubular hair as conducting vessels of the vegetable.

In addition, leaves of the pepper treated with 1000 mL WALF became yellow, wilted and eventually got defoliated. This may be due to the degradation actions of the treatment on chlorophyll content and undue secretion and self-digesting enzymes by parenchymatous cells of the pepper on middle lamella which eventually resulted into detachment of the leaves.

The treatment at that concentration may on the other hand be used as herbicides to control weeds. High chlorophyll content recorded in the leaves of pepper treated with 500 mL WALF+500 mL Water could suggest that the combination formed a nutritional synergy which enhanced chlorophyll and biochemical pigments formation. This assertion is in agreement with submission of Mohamed et al. (2008) who opined that that chlorophyll content and photosynthates are biochemical molecules formed as a result of plant metabolic activities. Lowest quantity of chlorophyll recorded in the pepper treated with 1000 mL of the filtrates might have disintegrated the chlorophyll content of the plants as reflected in the yellowing and eventually defoliation of the leaves due to its high concentration.

In the same trend, higher leaf area and net assimilation rate recorded in the pepper treated with the combination could be a measure of size of assimilatory system, accumulation and partitioning of photosynthates and economic relevance of the plant (Fanuel and Gifole, 2013). Studies of Subedi and Ma, (2005) and Rasheedat et al. (2017) had it that leaf area is one of the major components influencing plant productivity, dry matter production and grain yield of plant. Also, significant effect of application of 500 mL WALF + 500mL Water observed on leaf area, specific leaf area, net assimilation rate and relative growth rate of pepper could be a magnitude of total leaf area values which were higher in pepper treated using the treatment. The order of size of total leaf area values recorded in pepper treated with the combination could be responsible for high number of leaves recorded on the vegetable treated with the combination.

Conclusion

This study revealed that although wood ash liquid fertilizer has positive effects on growth and physiological attributes of the pepper, however, WALF at combination 500 mL WALF + 500 mL Water enhanced maximum growth and better physiological performance of the plant. In addition, 1000 Wood ash liquid fertilizer retarded morphological characters and physiological attributes of the pepper, therefore, combination of 500 mL wood ash liquid fertilizer (WALF) + 500 mL Water was regarded as optimal ratio (1:1) of the wood ash for pepper production.

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